

Evaluation of the Antioxidant and Neuroprotective Properties of Yellow Leaf Extract of *Terminalia Catappa* In Sleep-Deprived Rats

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ABSTRACT

Sleep deprivation is increasingly recognized as a public health issue linked to cognitive dysfunction and neurodegeneration due to oxidative stress. This study explores the neuroprotective potential of yellow leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* (T. catappa) in a rat model of sleep deprivation. Samples were obtained from oke ado akintola area in Ogbomoso, Southwestern, Nigeria. It was washed, air dried and pulverized. Extraction was done using ethanol, the extract was concentrated using a rotary evaporator. 35 female wistar rats were used, which were acclimatized for 2 weeks and different dosages of extracts were administered for 2 weeks. The rats were divided into five groups: Group I (control), Group II (sleep-deprived untreated), Group III (sleep deprived + Vitamin C), Group IV (sleep-deprived + 100mg/kg of *T. catappa* extract) and Group V (sleep-deprived + 200mg/kg of *T. catappa* extract). Sleep was induced in rats using Modified Multi-Platform Method (MMPM) and was sacrificed using cervical dislocation; the brain tissue was collected for assay. Biochemical assays revealed that *T. catappa* caused significant biochemical changes. It decreases level of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE), Glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH), Malondialdehyde (MDA), and Nitric oxide (NO). Concurrently, it increases levels of Serotonin, Glutathione (GSH), and Superoxide dismutase (SOD). These findings suggest *T. catappa* yellow leaf extract as a potent neuroprotective agent with therapeutic promise in oxidative stress-related neural conditions.

Keywords: *Terminalia catappa*, sleep deprivation, oxidative stress, antioxidants, neuroprotection, Wistar rats

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a vital physiological process crucial for maintaining both physical and mental health. Chronic sleep deprivation has been increasingly associated with a range of adverse outcomes, including cognitive decline, mood disorders, and the progression of neurodegenerative diseases (Walker, 2019). As the global prevalence of sleep-related disorders continues to rise, there is growing interest in identifying natural therapeutic agents with neuroprotective properties that can counteract the detrimental effects of inadequate sleep. Herbal remedies have gained attention as promising alternatives to conventional pharmacological treatments for sleep disorders, due to their relatively low risk of dependency and side effects (Asnis *et al.*, 2016). In this context, *Terminalia catappa*, commonly known as Indian or tropical almond, has emerged as a plant of significant medicinal value. Traditionally used in various

cultures, particularly in Asia and the Pacific Islands, the leaves of *T. catappa* are known to contain a variety of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, and saponins, which exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects (Akinmoladun *et al.*, 2017). Although the therapeutic properties of *T. catappa* have been explored in treating skin conditions, liver diseases, and metabolic syndromes, its potential for mitigating the neurological effects of chronic stress and sleep deprivation remains relatively underexplored (Chandrasekhar *et al.*, 2017; Zhu *et al.*, 2018). The neuroprotective potential of plant-derived extracts has attracted significant scientific interest in recent years as a complementary approach to managing neurocognitive impairments and neuro inflammation. This study, therefore, seeks to evaluate the antioxidant and neuroprotective properties of yellow leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* in a sleep-deprived rat model. By examining its ability to modulate oxidative stress

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and neurochemical alterations associated with sleep deprivation, this research aims to contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of phytomedicines in the management of sleep-related neurodegenerative disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Authentication

Fresh yellow leaves of *Terminalia catappa* were collected from a mature tree located at Aderibigbe House, Oke Ado Akintola Street, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria. Botanical authentication was conducted at the Herbarium Unit, Department of Pure

and Applied Biology, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso and a voucher specimen was deposited under the accession number LHO 809.

Preparation and Extraction of Plant Material

The yellow leaves of *T. catappa* collected were thoroughly washed, air-dried at ambient temperature, and pulverized into a fine powder. A 500 g portion of the powdered sample underwent cold maceration in 2.5 L of ethanol for comprehensive phytochemical extraction. The resultant extract was filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure, using a rotary evaporator, and subsequently freeze-dried to obtain the crude ethanol extract.

Plate 1: Fruits, leaves and flower of *Terminalia catappa*

Determination of Antioxidant Activity

(a). DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The antioxidant capacity of the *T. catappa* yellow leaf extract was evaluated using the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay as described by Adeyemo *et al.* (2018). 0.1 mM DPPH solution in methanol was reacted with various concentrations of the extract (100–500 µg/mL). Each reaction mixture contained 1000 µL of sample and 500 µL of DPPH reagent, incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 518 nm against a methanol blank. Ascorbic acid was used as the reference standard. Percentage inhibition was calculated using:

Where A_c = Absorbance of Control and A_s = Absorbance of sample.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{A_c - A_s}{A_c} \times 100$$

(b). Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay.

The FRAP activity was assessed following Benzie and Strain (1996). Varying concentrations of the extract (100–500 µg/mL) were mixed with 1000 µL of FRAP working reagent and incubated for 6 minutes at room temperature. Absorbance was recorded at 593 nm. A standard curve was generated using ascorbic acid and ferrous sulfate solutions of equivalent concentrations.

FRAP

$$(\mu\text{M})_{\text{value}} = \frac{\text{Abs test sample}}{\text{Abs standard}} \times [\text{FRAP}]_{\text{std}} (\mu\text{M})$$

(c). Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Assay.

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity was determined using the phenanthroline-based method (Gulcin *et al.*, 2009). The assay mixture (2.5 mL total volume) contained 1,10-phenanthroline, sodium phosphate buffer, Fe₂ SO₄, H₂O₂, and varying extract concentrations (100–500 µg/mL). After 30-minute incubation at room temperature, absorbance was measured at 536 nm. Ascorbic acid served as the standard. Percentage scavenging was calculated as:

Where AbCtrl= Absorbance of the Control,
AbSample= Absorbance of the sample or Standard

$$\text{Scavenging Activity (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{AbCtrl} - \text{AbSample}}{\text{Abs Ctrl}} \right] \times 100$$

(d). Total Antioxidant Capacity (TAC)

TAC was determined using the phosphomolybdenum method (Baydar *et al.*, 2007). Equal volumes of 0.6 M sulfuric acid, 28 mM sodium phosphate, and 4 Mm ammonium molybdate were mixed to form the reagent. A 100 µL aliquot of extract (100–500 µg/mL) was added to 1000 µL of the reagent and incubated at 95°C for 60 minutes. Absorbance was read at 695 nm after cooling. Antioxidant activity was extrapolated from a standard curve prepared using ascorbic or gallic acid and expressed as mg equivalent per g extract.

Evaluation of Neuroprotective Properties of *T. catappa***A. Experimental Animals and Grouping**

Female Wistar rats (150–200 g) were procured from the Physiology Department, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology. The rats were kept under standard laboratory conditions (12 h light/dark cycle, ambient temperature and humidity, with ad libitum food and water) and were acclimatized for two weeks. Experimental protocols were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee. Rats were randomly divided into five groups (n = 7 per group):

Group I: Control (non-sleep deprived)

Group II: Sleep-deprived only (SD)

Group III: Sleep-deprived + Vitamin C (200 mg/kg)

Group IV: Sleep-deprived + extract of *T. catappa* (100 mg/kg) (D100)

Group V: Sleep-deprived + extract of *T. catappa* (200 mg/kg) (D200)

Extracts and control solutions were administered orally once daily.

B. Induction of Sleep Deprivation

Sleep deprivation was induced for 12 hours daily (7 a.m.–7 p.m.) over two weeks using the Modified Multiple Platform Method (MMPM). Rats were placed in water tanks (120 × 60 × 45 cm) containing small platforms (6 cm diameter) with water maintained 1 cm below the platform surface. Rats fell into the water upon attempting to enter deep sleep, thus preventing sustained sleep.

C. Post-Deprivation Handling and Tissue Collection

Following the deprivation period, animals were allowed 12 hours of recovery before euthanasia. Brain tissues were excised, homogenized, and analyzed for key biochemical markers of neurodegeneration and oxidative stress.

D. Neuro biochemical Assays**(i). Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Activity**

Measured using Ellman method, which detects thiocholine from acetylthiocholine hydrolysis. Thiocholine reacts with DTNB to form a yellow chromophore (412 nm). Enzyme activity was expressed as µmol substrate hydrolyzed per minute per mg protein.

(ii). Glutamate Dehydrogenase (GDH) Activity

Quantified via the reduction of NAD⁺ to NADH during glutamate deamination (Lee & Lardy, 1965). Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm; enzyme activity calculated using NADH's molar extinction coefficient (6.22 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

(iii). Serotonin Quantification

Performed using HPLC with electrochemical detection (Jacobson *et al.*, 1996). Brain homogenates in Perchloric acid were centrifuged and filtered. Serotonin was separated via reverse-phase column and quantified by comparison with standards.

(iv). Glutathione (GSH) Concentration

Measured by reaction with DTNB forming 5-thio-2-nitrobenzoate, detectable at 412nm (Beutler *et al.*, 1963). The values were compared to a standard GSH calibration curve.

Plate 2: Modified Multi-Platform Method (MMPM),

(v). Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity

Assessed based on the enzyme's ability to inhibit the auto-oxidation of epinephrine at pH 10.2 (Misra & Fridovich, 1972). Absorbance was measured at 480 nm. One unit of SOD was defined as the amount causing 50% inhibition of epinephrine oxidation.

(vi). Nitric Oxide (NO) Concentration

Determined via the Griess reaction, which detects nitrite as a stable end-product of NO metabolism (Grisham *et al.*, 1996). The pink azo compound formed was measured at 540 nm and quantified using sodium nitrite standards.

(vii). Malondialdehyde (MDA) Level

Assessed using the TBARS assay (Ohkawa *et al.*, 1979). MDA reacts with thiobarbituric acid under high heat to form a colored complex detectable at 532 nm. Concentrations were derived from a standard curve of tetraethoxypropane.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antioxidant Activity of Yellow Leaf Extract of *Terminalia catappa*

The antioxidant capacity of *Terminalia catappa* yellow leaf extract was evaluated using hydroxyl radical scavenging, DPPH radical scavenging, and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assays, all of which revealed notable activity in a concentration-dependent manner. In the hydroxyl radical scavenging assay, the extract demonstrated moderate activity with a maximal inhibition of 56.87% at 250 µg/mL and an IC₅₀ of 209.81 µg/mL. These results, while indicating appreciable radical neutralization potential, suggest moderate potency compared to more commonly studied antioxidants such as *Azadirachta indica* (IC₅₀ = 180 µg/mL) (Alzohairy, 2016) and *Moringa oleifera* (Verma *et al.*, 2009). The decreasing absorbance values with increasing extract concentration reflect effective scavenging of hydroxyl radicals. The FRAP assay further confirmed the extract's robust antioxidant capacity, with a reducing power of 217.56 ± 1.01 mM Fe²⁺ equivalents/g dry weight. This value exceeds those reported for M.

oleifera and green tea (Carloni et al., 2013), approaching the antioxidant efficacy of ascorbic acid (Benzie & Strain, 1996). The high and reproducible FRAP activity suggests the presence of potent electron-donating compounds and underlines the extract's potential for nutraceutical or functional food applications. The DPPH radical scavenging assay also demonstrated strong activity, with inhibition ranging from 48.05% to 57.63% across the 50–250 µg/mL concentration range, and an IC₅₀ of 100.25 µg/mL. This value is notably lower than that of *Ocimum sanctum* (Prakash & Gupta, 2005) and comparable to *Terminalia chebula* (Bag et

al., 2013), suggesting significant free radical neutralization via hydrogen-donating mechanisms. The superior DPPH scavenging relative to hydroxyl radical scavenging suggests specificity toward nitrogen-centered radicals, consistent with the behavior of polyphenol-rich extracts (Prior et al., 2005). Collectively, the results highlight the yellow leaf extract of *T. catappa* as a promising source of natural antioxidants with broad-spectrum radical scavenging and reducing properties. These findings support its potential use in mitigating oxidative stress-related pathologies, warranting further bioactivity-guided phytochemical characterization.

Table 1: Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging activity of Leaf Extract of *T. catappa*

S/N	Concentration (µg/mL)	% Radical scavenging	IC 50 (µg/mL)
1.	50	29.5669	209.806
2.	100	32.9567	
3.	150	40.8663	
4.	200	48.0226	
5.	250	56.8738	

Table 2: Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) of Leaf of *T. catappa*

	FRAP (mM Fe ²⁺ /g)
T. catappa Extract	217.56 ± 1.01
Ascorbic Acid*	250.18 ± 0.85

Table 3: DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity of Leaf Extract of *T. catappa*

S/N	Concentration (µg/mL)	% Radical scavenging	IC 50 (µg/mL)
1.	50	48.0465	100.2545
2.	100	49.8605	
3.	150	51.814	
4.	200	54.51165	
5.	250	57.6279	

Modulation of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Activity

This study evaluated the neuroprotective potential of *Terminalia catappa* leaf extract on AChE activity in sleep-deprived rats. Sleep deprivation significantly increased AChE activity in the hippocampus (Group II) compared to the control group (Group I), indicating cholinergic disruption associated with cognitive impairment. Treatment with *T. catappa* at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V)

significantly reduced AChE activity in a dose-dependent manner ($p < 0.05$), suggesting restoration of cholinergic function, likely through antioxidant mechanisms. Similarly, Vitamin C (Group III) also reduced AChE activity, consistent with its known antioxidant role. Given Vitamin C's well-established antioxidant properties, the similar trend observed with *T. catappa* highlights its therapeutic potential in preserving acetylcholine availability and improving cognitive resilience to sleep loss.

Figure 1: Effect of *T. catappa* Leaf Extract on Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Activity in Sleep Deprived Rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C; T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Modulation of Glutamate Dehydrogenase (GDH) Activity

Sleep deprivation significantly increased GDH activity in rats (Group II), indicating glutamate metabolism dysregulation and oxidative stress, consistent with excitotoxicity linked to neurodegeneration. Treatment with *Terminalia*

catappa extract at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V) significantly reduced GDH activity ($p < 0.05$) in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting its potential to modulate glutamatergic neurotransmission and mitigate excitotoxic damage. Vitamin C (Group III) showed a similar reduction, reinforcing the role of antioxidants in protecting against sleep deprivation-induced neurotoxicity. The findings support the therapeutic relevance of *T. catappa*, likely due to its antioxidant phytochemicals, in managing glutamate-related cognitive dysfunction.

Figure 2: Effect of *Terminalia catappa* Leaf Extract on Glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) activities in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C; T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Restoration of Serotonin Levels by *Terminalia catappa* in Sleep-Deprived Rats

Chronic sleep deprivation significantly reduced serotonin levels in rats (Group II) compared to controls (Group I), indicating disrupted serotonergic signaling linked to mood and cognitive dysfunction (Bai et al., 2015). Treatment with *Terminalia catappa* extract at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and

V) significantly restored serotonin levels ($p < 0.05$), showing dose-dependent efficacy likely mediated by its antioxidant phytochemicals identified in GC-MS analysis. Vitamin C (Group III) produced a similar effect, consistent with its known neuroprotective role

in enhancing serotonin biosynthesis and combating oxidative stress (Vijayan et al., 2017). These findings suggest that *T. catappa* may serve as a natural therapeutic agent for managing sleep deprivation-induced serotonergic dysfunction.

Figure 3: Effect of *Terminalia catappa* Leaf Extract on Serotonin level in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C; T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Modulatory Effect of *Terminalia catappa* on Glutathione Levels

Chronic sleep deprivation significantly reduced glutathione (GSH) levels by ~42% in rats (Group II) compared to controls (Group I), indicating severe oxidative stress and impaired redox homeostasis. Treatment with *Terminalia catappa* extract at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V) restored

GSH levels by 68% and 89%, respectively ($p < 0.05$), in a dose-dependent manner. This effect is attributed to the extract’s antioxidant phytochemicals, such as flavonoids and tannins, known to scavenge free radicals and enhance endogenous antioxidant defenses. Vitamin C (Group III) showed a comparable 82% increase in GSH levels ($p < 0.05$), supporting its known antioxidant role (Harrison et al., 2009). The similar efficacy of *T. catappa* and Vitamin C underscores the extract’s therapeutic potential in mitigating oxidative damage caused by sleep loss.

Figure 4: Effect of *Terminalia catappa* Leaf Extract on Glutathione level in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C; T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Effect of *Terminalia catappa* on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity in Sleep-Deprived Rats
Chronic sleep deprivation significantly reduced SOD activity in rat brain tissues (Group II) compared to

non-deprived controls (Group I) ($p < 0.05$), indicating weakened antioxidant defense and increased oxidative stress. Administration of *Terminalia catappa* extract at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V) significantly restored SOD activity in a dose-dependent manner. The higher dose showed a more pronounced effect, similar to Vitamin C (Group III), a known antioxidant (Vijayan et al., 2017). These

improvements are likely due to *T. catappa*'s flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which enhance endogenous antioxidant enzyme expression and scavenge free radicals (Bai et al., 2015). The findings highlight *T. catappa*'s neuroprotective potential in reversing sleep deprivation-induced oxidative damage through enhancement of SOD activity.

Figure 5: Effect of *Terminalia catappa* Leaf Extract on Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C; T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Modulatory Effects of *Terminalia catappa* on Nitric Oxide (NO) Levels in Sleep-Deprived Rats

Sleep deprivation significantly increased brain nitric oxide (NO) levels in rats (Group II) compared to controls (Group I) ($p < 0.05$), indicating heightened oxidative stress and neuroinflammation due to dysregulated NO metabolism. This aligns with prior evidence linking excess NO to neuronal damage via reactive nitrogen species (Bai et al., 2015). Treatment

with *Terminalia catappa* extract at 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V) significantly reduced NO levels in a dose-dependent manner, likely through inhibition of inducible nitric oxide synthase by antioxidant phytochemicals such as flavonoids and polyphenols (Vijayan et al., 2017). Vitamin C (Group III) showed a comparable reduction, supporting its known role in modulating oxidative and inflammatory pathways. These findings highlight *T. catappa*'s potential to restore redox balance and mitigate neuroinflammation associated with sleep deprivation.

Figure 6: Effect of *Terminalia catappa* Leaf Extract on Nitric oxide (NO) concentration in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C;
T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

Attenuation of Lipid Peroxidation by *Terminalia catappa* in Sleep-Deprived Rats

Sleep deprivation significantly increased malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in rats (Group II) compared to controls (Group I) ($p < 0.05$), indicating elevated lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress—consistent with prior findings linking sleep loss to ROS-mediated membrane damage (Bai et al., 2015). Treatment with *Terminalia catappa* extract at 100

mg/kg and 200 mg/kg (Groups IV and V) significantly reduced MDA levels in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting effective inhibition of oxidative damage. This effect is attributed to the extract's antioxidant phytochemicals—flavonoids and phenolics—which scavenge free radicals and suppress lipid peroxidation (Vijayan et al., 2017). Vitamin C (Group III) showed a similar reduction, supporting its role as a potent antioxidant. These results underscore the neuroprotective potential of *T. catappa* in mitigating sleep deprivation-induced oxidative stress.

Figure 7: Effect of *Terminalis catappa* Leaf Extract on Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in Sleep-deprived rats

Where SD= Sleep deprived rats; Vit.C= Vitamin C;
T.C= *Terminalia catappa*

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the protective effects of *Terminalia catappa* on various biochemical markers of oxidative stress in sleep-deprived rats. The results show that sleep deprivation significantly altered several critical parameters causing significant biochemical changes. It decreases level of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE), Glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH), Malondialdehyde (MDA), and Nitric oxide (NO). Concurrently, it increases levels of Serotonin, Glutathione (GSH), and Superoxide dismutase (SOD), further highlighted the oxidative and neurochemical imbalances caused by sleep deprivation. These results suggest that *Terminalia catappa* possesses potent antioxidant and neuroprotective properties, which may counteract the adverse effects of sleep deprivation.

REFERENCE

- Walker, M: Why we sleep, Unlocking the power of sleep and dreams, Scribner, (2019)
- Asnis GM, Thomas M, & Henderson MA: Pharmacotherapy treatment options for insomnia, A primer for clinicians, International Journal of Molecular Sciences, (2016), 17(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms17010050>
- Akinmoladun AC, Ibukun EO, Afor E, Akinrollu B, Onibon T, Akinbami A, Obuotor E M: Proximate, phytochemical, and in vitro antimicrobial properties of *Cnidioscolus aconitifolius* (Mol.) I. M. Johnst leaves, Journal of Microbiology and Antimicrobials, (2017), 9(4), 32–38. doi:10.5897/JMA2016.0446.
- Chandrasekhar K, Kapoor J, & Anishetty S: Neuro-modulatory potential of herbal adaptogens under chronic stress conditions, Journal of Ethnopharmacology, (2017), 200, 156–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2017.01.050>

5. Zhu W, Ding Y, Kong W, Li T, Chen H: Docosahexaenoic Acid (DHA) Provides Neuroprotection in Traumatic Brain Injury Models via Activating Nrf2 ARE Signaling. *Inflammation*, (2018), 41(4), 1182–1193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10753-018-0765-z>.
6. Adeyemo OA, Osibote E, Adedugba A, Bhadmus O A, Adeosun A A, Allison M O: Antioxidant Activity, Total Phenolic Contents and Functional Group Identification of Leaf Extracts among Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) Accessions, *Journal of the Nigerian Society for Experimental Biology*, 18(2), 83–91.
7. Benzie IF, & Strain J J: The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”, The FRAP assay, *Analytical Biochemistry*, (1996), 239(1), 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1996.0292>
8. Gülçin, İ: Antioxidant activity of L adrenaline, An activity structure insight, *Chemical-Biological Interactions*, (2009), 179(1), 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2008.09.005>
9. Baydar N G, Özkan G, Yaşar S: Evaluation of the antiradical and antioxidant potential of grape extracts, *Food Control*, (2007), 18(9), 1131–1136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2006.06.011>
10. Ellman GL, Courtney KD, Andres V, Feather-Stone RM: A new and rapid colorimetric determination of acetylcholinesterase activity, *Biochemical Pharmacology*, (1961), 7(2), 88–95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952\(61\)90145-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952(61)90145-9)
11. Lee YP, Lardy HA: Influence of thyroid hormones on L alpha glycerophosphate dehydrogenase and other dehydrogenases in various organs of the rat, *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, (1965), 240(4), 1427–1436.
12. Jacobson JL, Jacobson SW: Intellectual impairment in children exposed to polychlorinated biphenyls in utero, *The New England Journal of Medicine*, (1996), 335(12), 783–789. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199609123351104>
13. Beutler E, Duron O, Kelly BM: Improved method for the determination of blood glutathione. *Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine*, (1963), 61, 882–888.
14. Misra HP, Fridovich I: The role of superoxide anion in the autoxidation of epinephrine and a simple assay for superoxide dismutase *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, (1972), 247(10), 3170–3175. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(19\)45228-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(19)45228-9)
15. Miles AM, Bohle DS, Glassbrenner PA, Hansert B, Wink DA, Grisham MB: Modulation of superoxide-dependent oxidation and hydroxylation reactions by nitric oxide, *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, (1996), 271(40), 24233–24238.
16. Ohkawa H, Ohishi N, Yagi K: Assay for lipid peroxides in animal tissues by thiobarbituric acid reaction, *Analytical Biochemistry*, (1979), 95(2), 351–358. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697\(79\)90738-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697(79)90738-3)
17. Alzohairy MA: Therapeutic role of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) and their active constituents in disease prevention and treatment, *Evidence Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2016, Article ID 7382506. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/7382506>
18. Verma AR, Vijayakumar M, Mathela C S, Rao CV: In vitro and in vivo antioxidant properties of different fractions of *Moringa oleifera* leaves, *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, (2009), 47(9), 2196–2201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2009.06.005>
19. Carloni P, Tiano L, Padella L, Bacchetti T, Customu C, Kay A, Damiani E: Antioxidant activity of white, green and black tea obtained from the same tea cultivar, *Food Research International*, (2013), 53(2), 900–908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2012.07.057>
20. Benzie IF, Strain J J: The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”, The FRAP assay, *Analytical Biochemistry*, (1996), 239(1), 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1996.0292>
21. Prakash P, Gupta N: Therapeutic uses of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn (Tulsi) with a note on eugenol and its pharmacological actions: a short review. *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, (2005), 49(2), 125–131.
22. Bag A, Kumar BS, Kumar PN, Chattopadhyay RR: Anti-inflammatory, anti-lipid peroxidative, antioxidant and membrane stabilizing activities of hydroalcoholic extract of *Terminalia chebula* fruits *Pharmaceutical Biology*, (2013), 51(12), 1515–1520. <https://doi.org/10.3109/13880209.2013.799709>

23. Prior RL, Wu X, Schaich K: Standardized methods for the determination of antioxidant capacity and phenolics in foods and dietary supplements, *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, (2005), 53(10), 4290–4302. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0502698>
24. Bai Y, Mao QQ, Qin H, Zhong XM, Ren SP, Lai YC, & Yang L: Antidepressant-like effect of ethanol extract from *Terminalia catappa* leaves in mice, Evidence for involvement of the serotonergic system, *Journal of Neurochemistry*, (2015), 135(2), 225–236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnc.13220>
25. Vijayan VK, Mohapatra SC, Rao DN, & Thakur AK: Role of oxidative stress in pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases and therapeutic interventions, *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2017, Article ID 9247947. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/924794>
26. Harrison FE, Hosseini AH, McDonald MP, May JM: Vitamin C reduces spatial learning deficits in middle-aged and very old APP/PSEN1 transgenic and wild-type mice, *Pharmacology, Biochemistry and Behavior*, (2009), 93(4), 443–450. doi: 10.1016/j.pbb.2009.06.006.

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